

Machine Learning and Applications: An International Journal (MLAIJ)

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Call for Papers

Machine Learning and Applications: An International Journal (MLAIJ) is a quarterly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of the machine learning. The journal is devoted to the publication of high quality papers on theoretical and practical aspects of machine learning and applications. The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on machine learning advancements, and establishing new collaborations in these areas. Original research papers, state-of-the-art reviews are invited for publication in all areas of machine learning.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the journal by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of machine learning.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to the following:

- Applications
- Learning in knowledge-intensive systems
- Learning Methods and analysis
- Learning Problems

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail: mlaijournal@airccse.org. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : May 12, 2018**
- Notification : June 12, 2018
- Final Manuscript Due : June 20, 2018
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief